

THE USE OF ICT IN EDUCATION AND ITS ROLE AND IMPORTANCE IN LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

In this article you will learn about the role and importance of foreign languages in our lives and in our exchange of information. In this process, we can learn more about the extent to which we need ICT tools. In this regard, you can get acquainted with the decisions and orders of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their current results

Key words

ICT, acquainted, challenge, discuss, public, regards.

Introduction

Today, general education schools are perhaps one of the most important tasks in the whole country to teach foreign language and their main role. We know that today the world is developing rapidly. Of course, the role and importance of language in this is incomparable, because language is a means of communication and exchange of ideas. Without language, people lose the ability to understand and comprehend each other. There are so many languages in the world. Each country has its own language exchange tool.

Main body

There are few world languages in the world. For example, one of them is English. World-renowned brands, companies, organizations, big meetings are held in this language. Therefore, there is a great demand for it in our country, because our country must be among the developed countries. The main task in general education schools is to teach a foreign language and develop its method. at the same time all the necessary conditions are being created for the schools in accordance with this task. It is safe to say that the Decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Abduganievich Karimov "No. 1875 of December 10, 2012" is one of the key factors in raising and developing the level of foreign language skills of young people. One of the requirements for modern professionals today is to be able to use information and communication technologies. what we know and understand today does not meet the demands of tomorrow. Because every field of information communication is developing rapidly. As this development progresses, new technologies are being introduced in the education system. which in turn requires the specialist to be more demanding and diligent. In the process of learning from information technology, it is necessary not only to focus on a specific task. In other words, as a comment to the above-mentioned opinion, we should promote the use of educational techniques and taking into account the psychological aspect of the child's age.

If we teach without the use of modern technology, it will also have an impact on its effectiveness, because if we organize our lesson using technology, it will be fun and of course it will also save time.

In this regard, there are resolutions and decrees of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich. One of them was the resolution "On measures to further improve the system of organizing foreign languages." It should be noted that in the framework of the implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and the National Program of Personnel Training in the country will be created a system aimed at further integration of the republic into the world community

More than 51.7 thousand foreign language teachers have been trained in English, German and French multimedia textbooks for grades 5-9. Electronic resources for organizing English in primary school have been prepared. However, the analysis of the current system of organizing the study of foreign languages shows that educational standards, curricula and textbooks are in line with modern requirements. Government does not fully meet the demand for the use of information and media technologies. education is conducted mainly in traditional methods.

The organization of continuous learning of foreign languages at all stages of the education system, as well as the training of teachers and the provision of modern teaching materials require further improvement. By introducing advanced teaching methods using modern pedagogical and information communication technologies, teaching the younger generation in foreign languages will radically improve the system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently, and on this basis will use their achievements in world civilization and international information resources. In order to create conditions and opportunities for the development of cooperation and dialogue: 1. It should be noted that from the 2013/2014 academic year: in all regions of the country, foreign languages, mainly English, will be taught in the form of games and oral lessons from the first grades of secondary schools, and from the second grade onwards, learning the alphabet, reading and grammar; some special subjects, especially technical and international specialties, are taught in foreign languages in educational institutions;

(Paragraph 3 of item 1 as amended by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-3 of November 9, 2021 - National Database of Legislation, November 9, 2021, No. 06/21/3/1037.

We know that a foreign language, i.e. English, is mainly taught in 4 skills. these (listening, reading, writing, and speaking). without the use of technology, we cannot achieve high success in this field. for example, we first want to focus on the importance of the use of information technology and their role in the listening organic process, which is one of these 4 skills, and then move on to classifying other examples and results.

Listening

It is clear from its name that in the process of listening and understanding, of course, we use CD players, computers, TVs and similar technologies. we need to pay attention to how well the tuner's vocabulary pronounces words and adheres to their grammatical structure in the listening process, and how we can be like real native speakers when we speak. In order to achieve high results in this round, first of all, of course, we will use the Internet to search for the information and databases we need, and we will receive online master classes in this language from the original experts. it will not fail to show its effect. telephones and headphones help us when we are busy with any work on the street. we listen to different podcasts. or if we take the lesson process as an

example, the number of students at this stage will be large and we will of course use speakers and similar technology tools to make it sound better. or live communication with foreign native speakers using the Internet, as well as various correspondence with them, also help to express ourselves in this skill.

There are several pros and cons to using technology

1-At the same time, we can create opportunities for students with visual impairments to use technology, and we can bring them closer to the lectures.

2) Nowadays, the world is becoming more modern, and so is the younger generation. so we also need to take the lesson close to the worldview of the modern child because for them traditional lessons can be somewhat boring.

3) save time.

4) Enhancing the learning process using types of lessons such as power point, word, adding different elements will save time as mentioned above.

5) Download the topics and lectures explained on the board during the lesson on the computer.

6) We cannot imagine the launch of an online education system without ICT tools. because in this education system all lessons are conducted using ICT tools.

7) Recent research shows that people absorb 20% of what they hear, 30% of what they see and more than 50% of what they hear.

Negative effects

1) it can damage a child's speech activity For a long time his attention is focused on the computer or the phone. at which point he watches quietly. and if it exceeds the norm, it demonstrates its disadvantages.

2) The fact that schools in remote villages are not provided with technology is another example of this. I have personally witnessed that some schools do not have TVs or even some teachers do not have computers.

Conclusion

From this article we can conclude that. We need to use as many ICT tools as possible to make our lesson meaningful and effective. Therefore, schools should be provided with these tools in first place. Therefore, measures are being taken

References:

- 1.<https://uz.infocom.uz>
- 2.<https://moluch.ru>
- 3.<https://icta1125.blogspot.com>
- 4.<https://cyberleninka.ru>
- 5.<https://old.mitc.uz>
- 6.<https://maccase.ru>
- 7.<https://www.lex.uz>